

International Committee on Systematics of Prokaryotes

To whom it may concern,

This is an official request from the Executive Board of the International Committee on Systematics of Prokaryotes (ICSP, <https://www.the-icsp.org/>), which is asking for your help regarding deposits in your collection. This is phase one of the **Singleton Deposit Initiative**.

We are contacting you for inquiring about the status of certain deposits of type strains of species or subspecies whose names are validly published under the International Code of Nomenclature of Prokaryotes (ICNP). Culture collections are crucial for the nomenclature of bacteria and archaea, and your assistance would be much appreciated.

Rule 30(3)(b) of the ICNP indicates that as 'of 1 January 2001, the description of [...] new combinations previously represented by viable cultures must include the designation of a type strain [...] deposited in at least two publicly accessible culture collections in different countries'. This has the consequence that new combinations cannot be validly published if their basonym was based on a type strain and this strain is not available, or not available any more, from culture collections in at least two distinct countries. That is, names that reflect the assignment of species to other genera cannot be validly published in such cases although it might taxonomically be preferable.

This issue mainly affects names of species or subspecies validly published before 1 January 2001 because until then only a single type-strain deposit was sufficient (apart from those based on a preserved specimen, description or illustration). The situation may best be addressed by the exchange of cultures between culture collections. Alternatively, the Note to Rule 30(3) may be invoked. It indicates that in 'exceptional cases, such as organisms requiring specialized facilities (e.g., Risk Group/Biological Safety Level 3, high pressure requirements, etc.), exceptions may be made'. In such cases a deposit of the type strain in a single culture collection may be sufficient for valid publication.

The attached table shows deposits in your collection each of which is supposed to represent, or could represent, the type strain of one of those names of species or subspecies that were validly published under the ICNP before 1 January 2001. A complete description of all columns is found below. We would ask you to

- enter in the column *enter_status_in_your_collection* whether the deposit does not exist or never existed, whether it is not viable any longer, or whether it cannot be accessed for some reason, such as because of the

Nagoya protocol after 11 October 2014 or other national regulations (if the deposit never agreed with the features given in the original description, please provide this information, too);

- enter in the column *enter_status_in_your_collection* in the case of deposits marked with *yes* in the column *deposit_uncertain* whether they represent the type strain of the given species or subspecies (for deposits not so marked please enter a corresponding note of they do not represent the type strain of the given species or subspecies);
- enter in the column *enter_other_deposits_if_known* other accessible deposits of the same type strain in culture collections, if you are aware of them;
- enter in the column *enter_if_eligible_for_exception* the reasons, if any, for the strain being eligible for an exception as specified in the Note to Rule 30(3);
- enter in the column *enter_whether_transfer_possible* whether or not you would agree to sending a subculture of this strain to another collection for making it additionally available (this needs not be filled in if, e.g., your deposit is not viable any more, or has already been transferred, etc.);
- enter in the column *enter_e_mail_of_curator* the e-mail address of the person who provided information to us in case of further questions and for giving credit for that contribution in a publication;
- contact us in case of uncertainties or other questions or suggestions.

Please note that we are well aware that some of the requested information may be available from your catalogue. However, overall we are dealing with several hundreds of deposits to be investigated. Checking them in detail exceeds our resources, and in most cases we would end up with having to contact you anyway. This is why we are kindly asking for your contribution in this manner. Further phases of the Singleton Deposit Initiative may address similar issues, such as those caused by collections which ceased to operate.

Yours sincerely

Markus Göker, for the Executive Board of the ICSP

Descriptions of all columns in the attached table

deposit: The identifier of the deposit in your collection.

deposit_uncertain: When set to “yes”, this deposit is not currently displayed on the List of Prokaryotic Names with Standing in Nomenclature (LPSN, <https://lpsn.dsmz.de/>) because the data source is uncertain. You may want to tell us whether or not this is a deposit of the type strain of the species or subspecies whose name is given in the *taxon_name* column.

taxon_name: The taxon name whose type strain the deposit is supposed to represent. Occasionally more than a single taxon name may be listed per deposit.

authority: The authors of the name given in the *taxon_name* column.

enter_other_deposits_if_known: Should the same strain be already available from other collections, please enter the IDs of these other deposits here. Further action would not normally be required in such cases.

enter_status_in_your_collection: Please indicate whether the deposit does not actually exist or never existed or does not represent the type strain of the given species or subspecies (e.g., if the deposit never agreed with the features given in the original description). Particularly if the deposit is marked as uncertain, it may not actually represent the type strain or may even never have existed in your collection. If the deposit is not viable any longer, or if it cannot be accessed for some reason, please indicate this, too. If the deposit is not accessible because of the Nagoya protocol (as of 12 October 2014), because of other national regulations, or for other reasons, this should be indicated.

enter_if_eligible_for_exception: Please indicate here whether you believe the strain to be so difficult to handle that a deposit in a second collection is not currently feasible (see the Note to Rule 30(3) of the ICNP). If otherwise, leave this field blank. See also the next column.

enter_whether_transfer_possible: If possible and necessary the given type strain should be deposited in another collection. Please indicate here whether this is possible. See also the previous and the next columns.

enter_e_mail_of_curator: The e-mail address of the person who provided the information to the ICSP. Further action, such as re-depositing the strain in another collection, may also be taken. The resulting information to be sent to the ICSP would then include the accession number in that collection. The address is needed in case of questions and for giving credit for the provided information. The ICSP is interested in a variety of possible reports on these deposits, including reports on the outcome of an attempt to reactivate a culture, of conducting further checks on authenticity, of investigating legal issues, of depositing a subculture in another collection, or on the reasons for failing to do so. These reports would then be included in a joint publication.

deposits_shown_on_lpsn: All type-strain deposits currently shown on LPSN for this name, including the original strain identifier.

lpsn_record_no: The LPSN identifier for the name given in the *taxon_name* column.

publication: A textual description of the effective publication of the name given in the *taxon_name* column.

doi: The Digital Object Identifier of the effective publication of the name given in the *taxon_name* column.

pubmed_id: The PubMed ID of the effective publication of the name given in the *taxon_name* column. Values of 0 or lower are placeholders for missing PubMed IDs.